

Does Quantum Thermodynamics Dictate the Form of the Wavefunction $P(x)=W(x)W(x)$?

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The Schrodinger equation, a partial differential equation in $W(x,t)$ the wavefunction, was developed by Schrodinger from ideas of L. de Broglie and then given the interpretation of probability $\text{Probability}(x,t) = W^*(x,t)W(x,t)$ by M. Born.

In this note we ask whether the form $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ together with $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ such that $W(x)=\sum \text{over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ follows from quantum thermodynamics. In particular we concentrate on a quantum adiabatic transformation and insist it be one of no entropy change (as in (1)). The quantum spatial density of a particle in a box with infinite potential depends on L as $P(x) = 1/L \text{ density}(x/L)$ (bound state). Thus Shannon's entropy simply using $P(x)$ is L dependent. One needs $P(x)P(p)$ in addition to the first term changing by $\ln(1/L)$ and the second by $\ln(L)$ in order to remove L dependence during an adiabatic expansion. Similar considerations hold for the quantum simple harmonic oscillator (2). Thus the idea of a $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ which are linked (not independent) immediately follows from quantum thermodynamics as does the form of entropy $S=S_x+S_p$.

As a result it seems that if one deals with probability, one must not only consider conditional probability, but also a transformation function $f(px)$ which allows for inverse dependencies on p and x on a parameter. These ideas together with $P(p/x)=P(x \text{ and } p) / P(x)$ ((1a)) and $P^*(x/p) = P(x \text{ and } p) / P(p)$ lead, we argue, to the form $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\sum \text{over } p a(p) \exp(ipx)$.

We considered the approach of conditional probabilities in an earlier note (3), but did not give motivation for using them or the form $\exp(ipx)$. Rather we brought them in as assumptions, assuming that there should be both a $P(p)$ and $P(x)$. In this note, we argue that they seem to follow from the idea of quantum thermodynamics and a zero entropy change along an adiabatic path i.e. one which does not change the quantum bound state n .

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Quantum Mechanics

Classical Statistical mechanics contains the notions of $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. The latter is given by the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and the former by $C1 \exp(-V(x)/T)$ where T is temperature. A main point, however, is that $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ are decoupled or independent. For example, for a given T , $P(p)$ is the same regardless of the potential, only the spatial density changes at x .

In quantum mechanics, one has a state which depends on parameters. For example, for a particle in a box there is a spatial density shape $P(x)$ which scales as L in the sense that $P(x)=1/L \text{ function}(x/L)$ As a result $\text{Integral } 1/ dx \text{ function}(x/L)$ may be written in terms of the new variable $y=x/L$. A similar feature appears for the quantum oscillator although the parameter is \sqrt{mk} , k being the spring constant (3).

One may note how different the quantum $P(x)$ is from the classical one for a particle in a box with infinite potential walls. For the classical case, one has a flat distribution, but for the quantum case there are humps with no density at either wall. At this point we do not assume any knowledge of the existence of the Schrodinger equation or wavefunction.

Quantum Thermodynamical Considerations

The scaling of $P(x)$ with L i.e. $1/L$ function (x/L) leads to $-k P(x)\ln(P(x))$ containing a term $\ln(1/L)$. If one considers a quantum adiabatic change in L , the particle stays in the same quantum state, but entropy changes. If one wishes to have a quantum adiabatic change correspond to a thermodynamical adiabatic situation with no entropy change as in (1), one needs to make a modification. In (3) we suggested that:

$$S/(-k) = \int dx P(x)\ln(P(x)) + \int dp P(p) \ln(P(p)) \quad ((2))$$

First this suggests that one must deal with both the notion of $P(p)$ and $P(x)$. This is not to be expected from classical physics. A particle in a box has a fixed $| \text{momentum} |$ and so one would only consider $P(x)$. The idea ((2)) suggests all possible p (momentum) values so the fixed $| \text{momentum} |$ is really $| \text{average momentum} |$. Matters in quantum mechanics are more complicated.

This also imposes the condition that $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ must be correlated in the sense that if the first term contains a term $\ln(1/L)$, the second must contain $\ln(L)$. For the quantum simple harmonic oscillator the same scenario applies although the parameter differs.

[As an aside, if one knows the form of the Schrodinger equation, one may try to define a new variable e.g. $y=x/L$ such that the parameter disappears from the equation although the energy may be expressed as a new variable containing the parameter. One may see that this follows for the particle in a box with infinite potential walls, but also for the oscillator.]

If $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are correlated one would expect conditional probabilities to be involved. Secondly one might expect a transformation function of the form $f(px)$ (especially for the particle in the box). If $x \rightarrow x/L$, then $p \rightarrow Lp$ to keep px constant.

Conditional Probabilities

$$P(p/x) = P(x \text{ and } p) / P(x) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P^*(x/p) = P(x \text{ and } p) / P(p) \quad ((1b))$$

Furthermore p and x forms should be symmetric as neither variable is preferred.

$$P(p/x) P(x) = P^*(x/p) P(p) \quad ((3)) \quad \text{and} \quad \sum \text{over } x \quad P(p/x)P(x) = P(p) \quad ((4))$$

$$P(x) = \sum \text{over } p \quad P^*(x/p)P(p)$$

$$\sum \text{over } x_1 \quad P(x/p) P(p_1/x_1) P(x_1) = \delta(x, x_1) F(x)/G(p) G(x_1)/F(p) P(x_1) \quad ((5))$$

Write $F(x)=W(x)$ and $G(p)= a(p)$ (name changing) and let $\delta(x, x_1)$ be given by:

Sum over $p \exp(ip(-x+x1))$ This puts x and p on the same footing and uses a function of xp .

There is an extra issue, however, namely that $P(p/x)$ and $P(x/p)$ are complex while $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ are real, so caution is needed.

$P^*(p/x)P(x) = P(p)$ ((4)) Thus $\exp(-ipx)$ in the delta function is linked to a complex conjugate.

Then: $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx) / [\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)]$ to be normalized to 1.

The denominator, however, should be $W(x)$, thus:

$$W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx) \quad ((6))$$

How are $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ linked to $P(x)$ and $P(p)$?

$$P(x)/P(p) = P(p/x)/P^*(x/p) = a(p) \exp(ipx)/W(x) / [W^*(x)/a^*(p) \exp(ipx)] \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus: } P(x) = W^*(x)W(x) \text{ and } P(p) = a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((8))$$

The quantum result ((8)) seems to follow directly from the form of conditional probability, but we argue that the conditional probability approach follows from quantum thermodynamics in particular from forcing entropy to remain constant under a quantum adiabatic transformation in which a quantum state does not change i.e. there is a kind of scaling in space with the parameter e.g. x/L . Furthermore the form $\exp(ipx)$ not only is used to create a delta function, but ensures that the parameter change is "inverse" for the momentum portion so that $\ln(\text{parameter}) + \ln(1/\text{parameter})$ from S_x and S_p respectively insure that the parameter disappears. As a result, quantum thermodynamics also imposes $S = S_x + S_p$. This suggests that one needs a theory in which $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ are on the same footing which suggests conditional probability.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain the form of quantum mechanics i.e. $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ through quantum thermodynamics. We argue that if one imposes $dS = \text{no entropy change}$ for a quantum adiabatic process (as in (1)), then because $P(x) = \text{density}(x)$ may depend on a parameter e.g. $P(x) = 1/L \text{ function}(x/L)$ for a particle in a box with infinite walls, Shannon's entropy $-kP(x)\ln[P(x)]$ has a term $\ln(1/L)$. Thus keeping a particle in its same state (same density shape profile) as the parameter changes means entropy would change. This forces one to use $S = S_x + S_p$ with the added rule that S_x and S_p change under the parameter in inverse ways i.e. $\ln(1/L)$ and $\ln(L)$. In addition one must deal with both $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ and in a symmetrical way. For a particle in a box, classical thinking leads to a fixed absolute value of momentum and $P(x)$ not $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. In the quantum case the fixed absolute value of momentum is really linked to p average.

The adiabatic approach also suggests an $f(xp)$ type transformation to ensure that if $x \rightarrow x/L$ $p \rightarrow Lp$, but also that conditional probabilities govern the quantum situation. Using $P(p/x) = P(x \text{ and } p) / P(x)$ and $P^*(x/p) = P(x \text{ and } p)/P(p)$ and the idea of symmetry in p and x forms, one arrives at: $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$, $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ and $W(x) = \text{Sum over } p \ a(p)\exp(ipx)$ i.e. the quantum form.

References

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